

Factors Influencing Patient Delay in Pulmonary Tuberculosis in a Community Setting: A Cross-Sectional Study

Muh. Novryan Zeini Ardy^{1*}, Dyah Wulan Sumekar Rengganis Wardani², Bayu Anggileo Pramesona³

^{1,2,3} Master of Public Health Program, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Lampung, Jl. Prof. Sumantri Brojonegoro No. 1, Rajabasa, Bandar Lampung, Lampung 35145, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Delays in the treatment of Tuberculosis (TB) result in the failure to achieve the TB program's goals. The delay in TB treatment can be measured by patient delay and healthcare service delay. This study aims to analyze the factors influencing the occurrence of patient delay in pulmonary tuberculosis. The type of this research is quantitative with a cross-sectional approach. The research population consists of all suspected Pulmonary TB patients, totaling 182 patients, with a sample of 158 respondents using the proportional random sampling technique. This research was conducted in the Working Area of Maja Public Health Center, Marga Punduh District, Pesawaran Regency, Lampung, Indonesia, in September-October 2024. Data collection was conducted using a questionnaire. Data analysis was conducted univariately (frequency distribution), bivariately (chi-square), and multivariately (logistic regression). The research results indicate that there are factors associated with the occurrence of patient delay in this study, namely age factor (p-value <0.001), gender (p-value = 0.017), employment status (p-value <0.001), economic status (p-value <0.001), education level (p-value = 0.003), knowledge level (p-value = 0.023), smoking history (p-value = 0.022), distance from residence (p-value = 0.040), and cadre support (p-value <0.001). The dominant factor influencing the occurrence of patient delay in tuberculosis treatment is the employment factor (p-value = 0.019; OR (95% CI) = 21.5 (1.67-279.24). Advice for healthcare workers includes providing education about TB, particularly the cough symptoms suspected to be TB, especially in the smoking community, and efforts to change patients' perceptions about TB are essential to reduce the level of delay in seeking early healthcare.

KEYWORDS: Cross-sectional study, Patient delay, Public Health Center, Tuberculosis, Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis occurs in every part of the world. In 2020, the highest number of new TB cases occurred in the WHO South-East Asian Region, with 43% of new cases, followed by the WHO African Region with 25% of new cases and the WHO Western Pacific Region with 18%. In 2020, 86% of new cases occurred in 30 countries with a high TB burden. Eight countries contribute two-thirds of the new TB cases, namely China, India, Indonesia, Pakistan, the Philippines, Nigeria, South Africa, and Bangladesh (Orazulike et al., 2021). Tuberculosis is a contagious disease caused by the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* bacterium. Globally, tuberculosis cases amount to 6.4 million, which is equivalent to 64% of tuberculosis incidents. Tuberculosis remains one of the top 10 causes of death worldwide, with an estimated 1.5 million tuberculosis deaths globally (WHO, 2018). Tuberculosis cases in Indonesia remain one of the diseases with the highest incidence that still require government attention.

Based on the Global Tuberculosis Report 2019, it is estimated that there are 927,000 TB cases in Indonesia, ranking second in the world after India in terms of the number of TB cases. The number of new Tuberculosis cases in Indonesia in 2018 was recorded at 844,000 cases (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020). The number of TB case detections and treatments in Indonesia, referred to as Treatment Coverage (TC), was 64.5% in 2019. Lampung Province is one of the provinces in Indonesia that has not yet reached the TC target, which was 44.39% in 2018 and 54.3% in 2019. When viewed from each district or city, none of the districts or cities have achieved the target (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020).

The number of pulmonary TB Cases at Maja Public Health Center, Pesawaran Regency In 2021, there were 40 cases, in 2022, 59 cases, and in 2023, 80 cases. One of the community health centers in Pesawaran Regency had a TC percentage of 35.7% in 2021, 52.68% in 2022, and 67.11% in 2023. The TC percentage in Pesawaran Regency is still below the WHO target of $\leq 38\%$. TC describes how many TB cases are reached by the program; the higher the TC rate, the higher the likelihood of achieving TB elimination. A low TC also means that there are still many TB cases that have not been found and treated, indicating high TB

transmission in the district/city (Lampung Provincial Health Office, 2019). This illustrates that Indonesia is still far from the target of achieving 10 TB cases per 100,000 population by 2035.

The success of TB control efforts is measured by patient recovery and the effectiveness of TB management is seen from timely diagnosis and complete treatment. Treatment can be considered timely if individuals with TB symptoms immediately seek care at healthcare facilities. Patients are said to be delayed (patient delay) if the time taken from the first appearance of symptoms to the patient's visit to a healthcare facility is more than 21 days (3 weeks) (Jianming Wang et al., 2008). Individuals who delay accessing healthcare facilities are at risk of experiencing severe disease progression, increasing the risk of disease transmission in the community, higher mortality rates, and the risk of developing drug-resistant TB. Delays in TB treatment result in the failure to achieve TB program goals (Xia D, et al., 2016). Patient delay in seeking treatment is one of the main reasons for the high transmission rates and low disease detection rates. Pesawaran Regency still has low achievements in finding new patients with Acid-Fast Bacilli (AFB) positive pulmonary tuberculosis, as well as a low treatment success rate for AFB positive pulmonary tuberculosis, indicating that the achievements of the pulmonary tuberculosis program in Pesawaran Regency are still not successful. This study aims to analyze the factors influencing the occurrence of patient delay in pulmonary tuberculosis in a primary health care setting.

METHODS

This cross-sectional study recruited 158 suspected TB patients from a total population of 182 people taken from ten villages in the Working Area of Maja Health Center, Marga Punduh District, Pesawaran Regency, Lampung, Indonesia, through proportional random sampling in September - October 2024. In this study, the instrument used was a questionnaire. The knowledge questionnaire contains 18 questions with true or false answer options, which are answered by marking (√) the answer that the respondent considers correct. If the answer is correct, it is given a score of 1, and if it is incorrect, it is given a score of 0. The level of knowledge is categorized into two groups: a good level of knowledge with a score > 50% and a less good level of knowledge with a score ≤ 50%. Fifteen questions on the smoking history questionnaire have answer choices that can be marked (√) by the respondents. The education questionnaire, which contains statements related to the educational levels that TB patients have completed based on the respondents' last diploma. The TB cadre support questionnaire contains 5 questions regarding the role of healthcare workers in providing support and encouragement to patients, which involves offering assistance in the form of information or advice, practical support, or actions that can provide emotional benefits or impact the behavior of the recipients. This is something perceived by the respondents related to the actions taken by healthcare workers in providing encouragement, and the information given by the officers to conduct the BTA examination for pulmonary tuberculosis patients. Positive support if the research results yield a value ≥ mean, negative support if the research results yield a value < mean (Budiman and Riyanto 2021). The employment status questionnaire contains 5 questions regarding the respondents' employment status. The questionnaire on the distance to health facilities (Puskesmas) is considered close if the distance from home to the Puskesmas is ≤ 5km, and far if the distance from home to the Puskesmas is > 5 km. The independent variables in this study are age, gender, employment status, education level, knowledge level, smoking behavior, distance from residence, and cadre support. Meanwhile, the related variable is patient delay in pulmonary tuberculosis patients. Univariate data analysis (frequency distribution), chi-square, and logistic regression were used to examine the factors influencing the occurrence of patient delay in pulmonary tuberculosis. Ethical Clearance has been submitted to the Health Research Ethics Committee of Tanjung Karang Health Polytechnic with 001/Perst.E/KEPK-TJK/I/2025.

RESULTS

1. Univariate Analysis

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents (n = 158)

Variable	Category	n	Percentage
Age	≥45 years	71	44.9
	<45 years	87	55.1
Gender	Women	63	39.9
	Men	95	60.1
Status of employment	Not working	48	30.4

	Working	110	69.6
Economic status	<Minimum wage	66	41.8
	≥ Minimum wage	92	58.2
Education level	Low	99	62.7
	Higher	59	37.3
Knowledge level	Less	87	55.1
	Good	71	44.9
Smoking history	Not smoking	78	49.4
	Smoking	80	50.6
Distance from home	Far	86	54.4
	Close	72	45.6
TB cadres support	Less support	85	53.8
	Full support	73	46.2
Patient delay	Yes	54	34.2
	No	104	65.8

Based on Table 1, it is known that out of 158 respondents, the majority (55.1%) are young adults, male (60.1%), employed (69.6%), with an economic status ≥ UMK (58.2%), low education level (62.7%), poor knowledge level (55.1%), a history of smoking (50.6%), living far from the health facility (54.4%), receiving less support from TB cadres (53.8%), and patients with no delay (65.8%).

2. Bivariate Analysis

Table 2. The influence of respondent characteristics on patient delay in pulmonary TB patients (n=158)

Variable	Patient delay				p-value	OR 95% CI
	Yes		No			
	n	%	n	%		
Umur						
≥45 years	44	62,0	27	38,0	<0.001	12.48 (5.55-28,.4)
<45 years	10	11,5	77	88,5		
Gender						
Women	29	46,0	34	54,0	0.011	2.39 (1.22-4.69)
Men	25	26,3	70	73,7		
Status of employment						
Not working	28	58,3	20	41,7	<0.001	4.52 (2.19-9.32)
Working	26	23,6	84	76,4		
Economic status						
<Minimum wage	37	56,1	29	43,9	<0.001	5.63 (2.74-11.52)
≥ Minimum wage	17	18,5	75	81,5		
Education level						
Low	43	43,4	56	56,6	0.003	3.35 (1.55-7.21)
Higher	11	18,6	48	81,4		
Knowledge level						
Less	37	42,5	50	57,5	0.023	2.35 (1.17-4.69)
Good	17	23,9	54	76,1		
Smoking history						
Not smoking	34	43,6	44	56,4	0.022	2.32 (1.18-4.55)
Smoking	20	25,0	60	75,0		

Distance from home						
Far	36	41,9	50	58,1	0.040	2.16 (0.19-4.28)
Close	18	25,0	54	75,0		
TB cadres support						
Less support	41	48,2	44	51,8	<0.001	4.30 (2.06-8.97)
Full support	13	17,8	60	82,2		

Based on Table 2, it is known that the factors associated with patient delay incidents are age (p-value <0.001), gender (p-value = 0.017), type of occupation (p-value < 0.001), economic status (p-value < 0.001), education (p-value = 0.003), knowledge (p-value = 0.023), smoking history (p-value = 0.022), distance from residence (p-value = 0.040), and cadre support (p-value < 0.001).

3. Multivariate analysis

Table 3. Logistic regression analysis (n=84)

Variabel	Sig.	OR	95% C.I	
			Lower	Upper
Age	<0.001	19.01	5.82	62.01
Gender	0.095	0.08	0.01	1.54
Status of employment	0.019	21.59	1.67	279.24
Economic status	<0.001	9.57	3.18	28.78
Education level	0.082	2.77	0.87	8.76
Smoking history	0.369	2.27	0.38	13.59
Cadres support	<0.001	9.83	3.16	30.55

Based on Table 3, it is known that the variable with a p-value < 0.05 is the type of occupation variable. From these variables, it is known that the highest OR value is found in the employment variable, which is 21.59. It can be concluded that in this study, employment status is the most dominant variable after controlling for age, economic status, and TB cadre support.

DISCUSSION

According to Green and Kreuter (2005) in the Health Belief Model theory, age can influence an individual's perception of the risks and benefits of a health action. Adulthood tends to correlate with a better understanding of the importance of early diagnosis due to greater life experience and social responsibility. In line with the research by Maryoto (2021), there is a correlation between age and the delay in seeking treatment for pulmonary tuberculosis patients in Banyumas Regency (p-value = 0.003). The results of this study are in line with the research by Mekonen et al. (2014), which found that adult TB patients are more likely to adhere to treatment schedules and minimize delays compared to other age groups. A similar study by Islamiyah et al. (2015) found that adulthood is a protective factor against patient delay in pulmonary TB cases due to better health awareness.

This study shows the influence of gender on the occurrence of patient delay. A study in Yemen found that men are 2.03 times more likely to experience delays compared to women (WHO, 2006). The same was found in Uganda where men are 1.61 times more likely to experience delays compared to women (Buregyeye, 2014). However, in India, men reduce the risk by 0.42 times compared to women (Konda, 2014). These results are consistent with the research by Khan et al. (2019), which found that men have a lower tendency to experience patient delay compared to women, because they more often have autonomy in making health decisions. Research by Sari et al. (2021) in Indonesia also shows that women more often face barriers in accessing healthcare services, such as distance, cost, and time, compared to men. Additionally, a study by Abdul et al. (2020) shows that social factors such as household responsibilities and social stigma affect women's delays in seeking treatment.

According to the socio-economic theory in health, work can influence health behavior, including patient delay in seeking treatment. However, according to Anderson & Newman (1973) in the Behavioral Model of Health Services Use, although work can

influence access and health awareness, other factors such as education level, social status, and the availability of health facilities often have a stronger impact. Additionally, the Health Belief Model theory (Rosenstock, 1974) also shows that individual beliefs about health, rather than just employment factors, are more determining of their actions to seek treatment. According to Bourdieu's (1986) theory of capital, the employment factor is closely related to access to social and economic resources, which can influence individual health behavior. Jobs that provide a steady income and higher social status tend to improve access to healthcare services, thereby reducing the likelihood of patient delay. Moreover, Marmot's (2015) Social Determinants of Health theory explains that employment status is one of the social factors influencing an individual's well-being. A stable job can improve a person's social and economic conditions, increase awareness of the importance of health, and expedite the search for treatment. Therefore, working individuals have more resources to overcome barriers in accessing healthcare, which in turn reduces patient delay.

According to the Social Determinants of Health theory (Marmot, 2015), economic factors have a significant impact on health behaviors, including delays in seeking treatment. A higher economic status, such as having an income above the minimum wage, allows individuals to access better healthcare services, which in turn reduces patient delay. This theory is supported by research from Gakidou et al. (2017), which found that individuals with higher economic status have lower delays in seeking treatment, especially for chronic diseases like TB, because they have better access to healthcare facilities and the resources needed for treatment. Education is one of the social factors that influence health status. Individuals with low levels of education may have limited access to health information that can influence medical care decision-making (Marmot, 2015). The lack of knowledge about TB and its consequences often leads to delays in seeking treatment. In line with Maryoto's (2021) research, there is a relationship between education and the delay in seeking treatment for pulmonary tuberculosis patients. Patients with low education levels tend to experience delays in seeking treatment due to ignorance about the importance of early treatment and the ineffective dissemination of information among them.

According to the Health Belief Model proposed by Rosenstock (1974), knowledge about diseases greatly influences individuals' behavior in seeking treatment. Individuals who have a good understanding of TB disease symptoms and its consequences are more likely to seek medical treatment more quickly. This is because they have a better understanding of the risks posed by delays in treatment, making them more likely to act quickly. This model shows that the higher a person's level of knowledge about the disease, the lower the likelihood of patient delay. Furthermore, Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) also explains that an individual's knowledge and understanding of health, including TB, influence their beliefs and motivation to take preventive actions. Patients who have a better understanding of TB, such as its symptoms and long-term risks, will be more proactive in seeking timely treatment.

According to the Health Belief Model theory developed by Rosenstock (1974), individual behavioral factors, such as smoking habits, can influence how they react to disease symptoms and their willingness to seek medical treatment. Patients who smoke may be more aware of health issues related to the respiratory system and lungs, such as TB, because they have already experienced the negative impacts of smoking habits. This may encourage them to seek treatment more quickly when TB symptoms appear. However, another theory that focuses more on smoking habits suggests that although smokers may be more likely to seek treatment immediately, the smoking habit can also cause them to ignore emerging symptoms in the short term because they are already accustomed to respiratory issues. Therefore, although smoking can increase awareness of lung health issues, this habit can also serve as a barrier for individuals to promptly visit healthcare facilities if TB symptoms develop slowly.

The distance from home to healthcare services can affect patient delay. This is related to access to healthcare services. The farther the residence is from healthcare services, the longer the patient delay. It was found that based on previous research, patients who live more than 5 km away tend to experience longer delays compared to patients who live less than 5 km away (Huong et al., 2007). The Health Belief Model theory (Rosenstock, 1974) explains that geographical distance can affect an individual's decision to seek medical care. The farther the patient's residence is from the healthcare facility, the greater the barriers they face in accessing healthcare services. Distance can act as a barrier that affects their belief regarding the ease or difficulty of obtaining treatment, which can lead to delays in seeking medical care. Additionally, the Access to Care theory proposed by Pechansky and Thomas (1981) states that accessibility to healthcare services is influenced by geographical factors, including the distance of patients' residences from healthcare facilities. Patients who live far from healthcare facilities may find it difficult or burdensome due to the costs and time required to visit those facilities, which in turn can lead to delays in seeking treatment.

In the context of TB patients, support from health cadres can increase patients' awareness of TB symptoms and the importance of treatment, as well as encourage them to promptly visit healthcare facilities. Furthermore, the Health Belief Model theory (Rosenstock, 1974) explains that social support provided by health cadres can enhance individuals' perception of the severity of the disease and the benefits of treatment, as well as reduce barriers to seeking treatment. Cadres who provide emotional and practical support can help patients overcome fear or doubt in seeking medical care, which in turn reduces the likelihood of patient delay. This study is in line with the research conducted by Widiastuti et al. (2020), which shows that support from health cadres plays an important role in accelerating patients' decision-making to seek treatment. Cadres who provide information, motivation, and emotional support help patients become more aware of the importance of TB treatment, making them more likely to promptly visit healthcare facilities.

CONCLUSION

Factors related to the occurrence of patient delay in this study include age, gender, employment status, economic status, education level, knowledge level, smoking history, distance from residence, and cadre support. The dominant factor influencing the occurrence of patient delay in tuberculosis treatment is the employment factor. Advice for healthcare workers includes providing education about TB disease, symptoms of cough suspected to be TB, especially in smoking communities, and efforts to change patients' perceptions about TB disease are essential to reduce the level of delay in seeking early healthcare.

REFERENCES

1. Abdul, J. B. P. A. A., Adegbite, B. R., Ndanga, M. E. D., Edoa, J. R., Mevyann, R. C., Mfoumbi, G. R. A. I., de Dieu, T. J., Mahoumbou, J., Biyogho, C. M., Jeyaraj, S., Niemann, S., Lell, B., Kremsner, P. G., Alabi, A. S., Adegnika, A. A., & Grobusch, M. P. (2023). Resistance patterns among drug-resistant tuberculosis patients and trends-over-time analysis of national surveillance data in Gabon, Central Africa. *Infection*, 51(3), 697–704. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s15010-022-01941-5>
2. Andersen, R., & Newman, J. F. (1973). Societal and Individual Determinants of Medical Care Utilization in the United States. *The Milbank Memorial Fund Quarterly. Health and Society*, 51, 95-124. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3349613>
3. Bandura, A. (1986). *Social Foundations of Thought and Theory: A Social Cognitive Theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
4. Bourdieu, P. (1986). The Forms of Capital. In J. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education*
5. Buregyeye, E. 2014. *Delays in Diagnosis and Treatment of Pulmonary Tuberculosis in Wakiso and Mukono Districts, Uganda*. BMC Public Health
6. Gakidou, Emmanuela et al. (2017). Global, regional, and national comparative risk assessment of 84 behavioural, environmental and occupational, and metabolic risks or clusters of risks, 1990–2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *The Lancet*, Volume 390, Issue 10100, 1345 - 1422
7. Green, L. and Kreuter, M. (2005) *Health program planning An educational and ecological approach*. 4th Edition, McGraw Hill, New York.
8. Huong, dkk. 2007. *Delays in the diagnosis and treatment of tuberculosis patients in Vietnam: a cross-sectional study*. BMC Public Health, 7 (110), pp. 1-8
9. Islamiyah F. (2015). *Karakteristik dan Alasan Patient Delay pada Kasus TB BTA (+) di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Kecamatan Kramat Jati Jakarta Timur Tahun 2014*. Skripsi. Universitas Islam Negeri Syarif Hidayatullah. Jakarta.
10. Jianming Wang, Yang Fei, Hongbing Shen, Xu B. (2008). Gender difference in knowledge of tuberculosis and associated health-care seeking behaviors: a cross-sectional study in a rural area of China. *BMC Public Health*. 8 (354):1-7.
11. Konda S, Melo C, Giri P, Behera A (2014). Determinants of delays in diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis in a new urban township in India: A cross-sectional study. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 3(2): 140. doi: 10.5455/ijmsph.2013.011120131.
12. Kementerian Kesehatan RI. (2020). *Strategi Nasional Penanggulangan Tuberkulosis di Indonesia*. Jakarta:Kementerian Kesehatan RI.
13. Maryoto, M., & Khasanah, S. (2021). Hubungan Usia dan Pendidikan dengan Keterlambatan Pencarian Pengobatan Pasien

- Tuberkulosis Paru di Kabupaten Banyumas. *Viva Medika*, 14(02), 220-227.
14. Mekonen et al., Delay for First Consultation and Associated Factors among Tuberculosis Patients in Bahir Dar Town Administration, North West Ethiopia. *American Journal of Health Research*. 2 (4), 140-5.
 15. Marmot, M. G. (2005). *Social determinants of health inequalities*. The Lancet, 365(9464), 1099–1104. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(05\)71146-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(05)71146-6)
 16. Orazulike, N., Sharma, J. B., Sharma, S., & Umeora, O. U. J. (2021). Tuberculosis (TB) in pregnancy - A review. *European journal of obstetrics, gynecology, and reproductive biology*, 259, 167–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2021.02.016>.
 17. Penchansky, R., & Thomas, J. W. (1981). *The concept of access: Definition and relationship to consumer satisfaction*. Medical Care, 19(2), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005650-198102000-00001>
 18. Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). *Historical origins of the health belief model*. Health Education Monographs, 2(4), 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019817400200403>
 19. Widiastuti, N., Dwianto, W., & Sari, R. (2020). The influence of job characteristics on health seeking behavior in tuberculosis patients. *Journal of Public Health and Community Medicine*, 12(2), 91-98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/jphcm.2020.14.2.91>
 20. World Health Organization. (2006). *Diagnostic and Treatment Delay in Tuberculosis*. WHO.
 21. World Health Organization. (2018). Global tuberculosis report 2018. World Health Organization. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/274453>.
 22. Xia D, Zhang Z, Li X, Jiang C, Ma J, Ding S, Chen B, Guo R, Wen Y. (2016). Factors Associated with Patient Delay Among New Tuberculosis Patient in Anqing, China. *Biomedical Research*. 27(3):651-8.

Cite this Article: Ardy, M.N.Z. , Rengganis Wardani, D.W.S. , Pramesona, B.A. (2025). Factors Influencing Patient Delay in Pulmonary Tuberculosis in a Community Setting: A Cross-Sectional Study. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 8(1), pp. 543-549. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i1-57>